

**ONGOING REFORMS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF NEW
UZBEKISTAN**

Apseterova Sayatkhan Abdizhalievna

Primary school teacher of Nukus city secondary school No. 11

Turdymuratova Ulzada Mukhitdin-kyzy

Assistant of the Nukus branch of the Samarkand State University of Veterinary
Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology

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In New Uzbekistan, the foundations of the "Third Renaissance" are being laid. This goal cannot be achieved without improving the quality of education. On this occasion, on February 27, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Decree PP No. 4623 "On measures to further develop the field of teacher education", and now the issue of improving the quality of education in our republic has reached a new level. First of all, the issue of textbooks is important. The head of state set the task of introducing textbooks based on the experience of Finland, and work in this direction was systematically started.

At present, in the development of the education system of Uzbekistan, the experience of Finland, along with the experience of advanced foreign countries, occupies a special place. Because, if we consider the last decade, the Finnish state has achieved great results in all education systems. Of course, it is necessary to pay attention to what is behind such results, indicators and skills. Today, reforms in our republic are being carried out in parallel with the issues of the driving force of the education system, that is, the system of training teachers, which indicates the attention of our state to improving the quality of education.

A number of decisions and decrees have been adopted in the republic to improve the quality of teacher education and the system of training teachers.

For example, in accordance with the resolutions of the Resolution No. 4623 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 27, 2020 "On measures for the further development of the field of teacher education" and the Cabinet of Ministers No. 408 dated June 30, 2021 "On measures to organize the activities of the Uzbek-Finnish Pedagogical Institute of the Samarkand State University" in Uzbekistan, for the first time, the Uzbek-Finnish Pedagogical Institute was organized.

In order to get an answer to the question of how the phenomenon of Finland could improve our state education system, when looking at the educational processes and stages in Finland, this state system formed an education system based on humanism, i.e., humanity, as well as international statistics, the international standard of education and the stages of education. That is, an

eight-stage education system has been formed, and the most important of these systems are pre-school, secondary, general secondary education (the second stage of secondary education), vocational (vocational guidance) and higher education. When forming the education system in the Republic of Finland, special attention was paid to the role of the teacher. The fact is that programs based on international standards are developed taking into account immediate novelty and age characteristics, as well as attention to teachers. For example, there are two programs for preschool children: the first is educational, the second is preschool, which prepares individual six-year-old children for school on the basis of one-year educational programs. Also, school education is classified according to the first and second international standards, and developmental education is established for children up to the sixth grade. For children up to the sixth grade, a system for evaluating the knowledge taught and given is introduced not in relation to the student, but in relation to this knowledge. This, in turn, allows children up to the sixth grade to fully understand the events and phenomena taking place in the world, and to have their own opinion. Another important aspect of these experiments is the orientation of students in grades 7-9 towards the exact sciences.

In Finland, special attention is paid to the three-year and vocational education as the second stage of secondary education. Although one aspect of the three-year general secondary and vocational (professional) education is defined by law as three years, it can be defined as two to four years, depending on the ability of the student. This, in turn, provides an excellent opportunity for students to adapt in the profession.

In addition, educational activities have their own characteristics. The peculiarity lies in the fact that the primary attention in the educational process is given to motivational education. That is, the state strictly controls the child, the personality of the child and his attendance at school. Achieving this indicator is the result of close cooperation between the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture and the National Management System and the identification and timely elimination of existing problems.

Given the above, the reforms related to the education system in our country make it possible to introduce new opportunities and technologies into the education system. Thanks to the effective use of these reforms, our educational system meets the requirements of international standards, as a result of which we enter the international assessment system. The implementation of such reforms is based on the international standard classification, and the

introduction of standards within national qualifications will provide opportunities for training based on the international labor market. At the same time, the experience of Finland has a place to be in order to be able to continuously bring personnel from kindergarten to the system of general secondary and vocational education in close connection with the higher education system.

The implementation of such work helps to harmonize the demand for training in a particular area and regions with the local labor market. According to the experience of Finland, in the system of higher education, the development of standards that meet qualification requirements, within the framework of a single state policy, and the experience of qualification of a narrow range of specialties assigned to personnel by higher education institutions are being launched.

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